

The Media is *Not* the Message- the Relationships is: On the Effectiveness of Distance Treatment

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The fundamentals of a therapeutic relationship have not changed since Freud's day, but the opportunities for it has changed. Today psychodynamic treatment is now available anywhere there is tele-communications. But how effective is it?

The China American Psychoanalytic Alliance through its Research Grant Committee has been supporting the study of this very complex issue. To research something with many interdependent variables is best accomplished with expert and consumer opinions.

Our first empirical study was published in 2015. Gordon, Wang, and Tune, (2015) asked 176 CAPA faculty and treaters their opinions about the effectiveness of teaching, supervising and treating over videoconferencing (VCON) to Chinese students and patients. Our results indicated that the faculty and treaters felt that over-all VCON minimally reduces effectiveness and that individual client characteristics may be a significant factor in effectiveness. Most of the therapists in this study, about 60%, rated treatment to CAPA students over VCON as similar to in-person office work.

We then wanted to look at the issues that concerned the low raters of effectiveness. Gordon, Tune & Wang, (2016) found that treaters who gave low ratings of treatment effectiveness (about 40% of treaters) felt that video-conferencing mostly did not compare well to in-person psychotherapy in exploring the mental life of the patient. Nevertheless, low raters of effectiveness and higher raters of effectiveness generally agree that treatment over VCON is valuable since it offers high quality treatment to underserved or remote patients, and it is valuable when the patient is house-bound or travel would be impractical.

Our next step was to assess the Chinese consumers of distance training and treatment (Gordon & Lan, 2017). We surveyed our CAPA graduates who received their psychoanalytic treatment during their training. Ninety graduates who were currently seeing patients responded to our survey. They made excellent respondents since they are highly intelligent, high functioning consumers with an unusual degree of insight and objectivity into the effectiveness of their training and treatment as compared to the average psychotherapy patient. We used the Comparative Psychotherapy Process Scale (CPPS) along with our survey questions. We found that distance psychoanalytic training was highly effective. The number of years of CAPA distance education correlated significantly with the number of years of personal psychoanalytic treatment, and also with the number of years working psychoanalytically with patients. The degree the graduates use a psychoanalytic formulation was best predicted by a greater number of years in distance education and the more days a week in personal therapy. This supports the idea that practitioners are more likely to become psychoanalytic in their clinical practice when they

receive a longer period of training, as well as intensive psychoanalytic therapy themselves. The graduates' ratings of how they are currently practicing psychoanalytic psychotherapy were highly correlated with how their own therapists practiced psychoanalytic treatment, as measured by the CPPS items. Graduates highly rated the effectiveness of their own psychoanalytic therapy over VCON.

The CAPA graduates thought that the therapist variables (warmth, wisdom, empathy, and skillfulness) were much more important in the effectiveness of their treatment than whether the treatment was in-person or with VCON, or the cultural differences with their therapist (1= Not important; 7= Highly important).

Warmth of therapist	$M = 6.0$	$SD = 1.2$
Wisdom of therapist	$M = 5.9$	$SD = 1.1$
Empathy of therapist	$M = 6.4$	$SD = .85$
Skillfulness of therapist	$M = 5.4$	$SD = .96$
Cultural similarity of therapist	$M = 4.1$	$SD = 1.4$
The use of video-conferencing	$M = 3.9$	$SD = 1.5$

In conclusion, there is a good deal of support for distance training and treatment and that the issues of tele-therapy and cultural differences seem to be minor and analyzable. However, what remains is the importance of the qualities of the therapist regardless of culture or media. The next issue that needs to be studied is what patient personality factors interact with the use of tele-therapy.

References:

(Full copies of these articles are available on Research Gate or www.mmpi-info.com)

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